

ships. Thanks are due to Prof. W. Rahman for authentic samples.

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Fatty Acid Composition of Rayan Seed Oil

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MIMUSOPS hexandra Linn. (Rayan), a plant belonging to sapotaceae family, bears sweet edible fruit known as 'Khirani' in Hindi. The bark of the plant is used in fever and as a general tonic¹. The characteristics and fatty acid composition have been studied earlier using older techniques². We report here the characteristics and fatty acid composition of the seed oil of Rayan from Madhya Pradesh using glc technique for the first time.

Experimental

The seeds of *M. hexandra* were crushed and extracted with light petroleum ether to yield a pale yellow oil with a faint odour. The characteristics of the oil determined by standard methods³ are given in the Table 1. The oil was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and the unsaponifiable matter was separated. The mixed fatty acids extracted with diethyl ether were converted to their methyl esters by refluxing with anhydrous methanol containing concentrated sulphuric acid⁴.

Tlc and argentation tlc (12.5% aqueous AgNO₃) of fatty acids and methyl esters were carried out on silica gel G. Glc of methyl esters was carried out in a CIC Baroda gas chromatograph equipped with flame ionisation detector and dual columns packed with 10% DEGS on chromosorb (80-100 mesh) using nitrogen as carrier gas. The injection port, columns and flame ionisation detector block

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF RAYAN SEED OIL

Yield of oil (%)	24.0
Refractive index (at 30°)	1.4650
Saponification value	181
Iodine value	69
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	1.876
Fatty acids (%) :	
Myristic	0.25
Palmitic	20.86
Stearic	9.98
Oleic	52.66
Linoleic	16.85

were maintained at temperature 280, 180 and 180° respectively. Identification of the methyl esters was done using standard samples.

Results and Discussion

The characteristics and fatty acid composition of Rayan seed oil from Madhya Pradesh, being reported for the first time, are given in Table 1. It contains a high percentage of light coloured oil low in unsaponifiable content and is non-drying. Myristic acid (0.25%) is found in this variety and is reported for the first time. The oil is fairly stable and can be used for edible and other purposes after proper treatment.

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6',7'-Epoxyauraptene - A Coumarin from *Aegle marmelos*

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PREVIOUSLY we reported the structure of marmelide¹, a furanocoumarin from *Aegle marmelos*. Recent investigation of its root reveals the presence of another coumarin, 6',7'-epoxyauraptene (1).

